

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAN KHANTY'S FIGHT AGAINST THE DUNGARIAN INVASION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133393>

Abstract. *During the reign of Abdukarim-biy in Kokand, an insidious enemy, called the Zhungars, penetrates into the territory of Central Asia. They easily captured Dashti Kipchak and the northern regions of Central Asia and penetrated into the depths. At this dangerous moment, Abdukarim-biy organized the struggle of the resistance forces. Our ancestors heroically fought for their Motherland and freedom, the enemy was defeated on the battlefield, Kokand was liberated.*

Keywords: *kipchaki, kirgizy, kazakhi, karakalpaki, oblast' Tashkent, Kurama, Ferganskaya dolina, oblast' Ura-Tyube, Abdukarim-biy.*

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ БОРЬБЫ КОКАНСКИХ ХАНТОВ С ДУНГАРСКИМ НАШЕСТВИЕМ

Аннотация. *Во время правления Абдукарима-бия в Коканде на территорию Средней Азии проникает коварный враг, называемый джунгарами. Они легко захватывают Дашти-Кипчак и северные районы Средней Азии и проникают в глубь. В этот опасный момент Абдукарим-бий организует борьбу сил сопротивления. Наши предки героически сражались за свою Родину и свободу, враг был разбит на поле боя, Коканд был освобожден.*

Ключевые слова: *кипчаки, киргизы, казахи, каракалпаки, область Ташкент, Курама, Ферганская долина, область Ура-Тюбе, Абдукарима-бий.*

Today, in the history of peoples in Central Asia, the research of the historical processes that took place due to the attack of the Dzungor Khanate on our country in the 20s - 50s of the 18th century is considered to be an urgent issue. However, the relative scarcity of historical data on this issue makes it somewhat difficult to study this issue. However, the study of the history of migration processes in Central Asia would play a significant role in solving many problems.

In 1635, between present-day East Turkestan and Mongolia (the state of Mongolia), in the west of the Sin Empire of China at that time, the Jungor, Oyrot (Elyut in Russian sources) from the Mongol peoples, "Dzungor" or "Zengor", consisting of the Turks, the nomadic Mongol state called Dzhungaria came into existence and the Chu valleys, the bordering part of the Kazakh steppes, became subject to Dzhungaria, and the neighboring empires such as China and Russia were worried because a new powerful nomadic state was emerging between the two empires. was going.

During this period, the independent Fergana estate, whose center was Kokan, in the north-east of Movarounnahr, separated from the Ashtarkhanid state. After the Khanate of Dzhungaria conquered Eastern Turkestan, it occupied the Kazakh steppes, Chu Valley and Issyk-Kol, which are called "Dashti Kipchak" in the sources of that time. In such a situation, the fight against the attack of the settlers was organized by the ruler of Qukan, Abdukarimbiy. Abdukarimbi was the third ruler of the Thousand Dynasty and was the second son of Shahrukhbi (1709-1721), the founder of the Kokand Khanate. His reign lasted from 1733 to 1750, and this period played an important role in the subsequent rise of Kokan to the rank of khanate.

According to written sources, Abdukarimbi's accession to the throne was connected with the tragic end of his brother Abdurahimbi's life. Abdurahimbi, the ruler of Kokan (1722-1734), after the Samarkand and Shahrissabz military campaigns, suddenly fell ill and this illness ended with his death.

Sources and literature not only note that Abdurahimbi died in the city of Khojand, but also state that his brother Abdukarimbi was involved in his death. The struggle for power between the members of the Thousand Dynasty was intense. The date of Abdukarimbi's rise to power is indicated in different sources, the years 1733 and 1734 are mostly mentioned.

The period when Abdukarimbi occupied the throne of the Ferghana estate was characterized by complexity, first of all, it was necessary to keep the territories of Zomin, Jizzakh, Samarkand conquered by his brother. Six months after the conquest, Samarkand returned to the ownership of Bukhara, but from this period until 1742, it can be assumed that the remaining properties remained under the control of Kokan.

In addition, in front of Abdukarimbi, more complicated political problems arose, that is, the invasion of the Dzhungars into the territory of the country began. At the beginning of the 18th century, the rule of the Ming dynasty expanded to the Ferghana Valley and its neighboring regions, at the same time, the position of the Ming tribe's nobles strengthened day by day, and the central power became stronger. However, a little earlier, in 1635, the state of Dzhungaria was established in the northeast of China, and soon its borders reached the lands of the Kazakh and Kyrgyz tribes of the Dashti Kipchak. As a result, the Karakalpaks, Kazakhs and Kyrgyz who suffered from their invasion were forced to move their land and livestock to the interior of Movarounnahr.

In particular, the Kazakh scientist Ch. Researcher I.I. Strelkova writes about Valikhonov: "... the nomads' families panicked and fled, abandoning the corpses, goods and possessions that filled their paths." According to Khojamgulibek Balkhi, the author of "History of Kipchakkhani" from the last medieval written sources, on the banks of the Ayaguz River at the foot of the Kazakh steppes, in a fierce military conflict with the Kalmyks in 1718, the united Kazakh forces was defeated and the main part of them had to retreat to the southern Movarounnahr.

Among the peoples of Central Asia, the Dzhungor people are called Kalmyk (the ethnic names Kalmyk and Kalmyk are used equally for this people). The researchers assume that the name of the Kalmyk people is derived from the word "kalmyk", and the Turkic people gave this name to the Mongolian people without accepting Islam and remained in their own religion. In the Russian written sources and archival documents of that time, they are listed as "jungor", "dzhungor", "zungor" and "zengor". According to them, academician V.N. In the works of Tatishyev, it is given as follows: "... the Zyungors are from the Kalmyk people, they are great and extremely strong, they were previously divided into several taishi (principalities) and principalities... during the time of Taishi Sezen, they united and waged wars with China and Bukhara, Kazakhs won over them several times and forced them to pay taxes. He also captured several cities of Bukhara... At present, the Chinese have made peace with his son brave Galdan Syeren..."

The emergence of the Jungian state and its transformation into a kingdom posed a great danger, first of all, to Russia and Sin (China). As a result, the Russian Empire and the Chinese government tried to weaken this country in various ways. The Chinese army organized military campaigns against this country twice, in 1717 and 1731. But the Chinese side was defeated by the Jungians and had to sign a peace treaty.

Victory over China led to further strengthening of Dzhungaria. The Kalmyks began to march to the territories of the Kokhan Khanate after the territories of the Kipchak steppe. It fell to the ruler Abdukarimbi to fulfill the responsible task of preserving the Kokan Khanate.

Historical written source in the work of Khojamgulibek Balkhi: "... the Kalmyks from outside, like ants and locusts, cleaned the tails and hooves of their horses, first closed in on the Kazakh tribes and plundered them. Many tribes and clans of the Kazakh people were captured by Gog and Magog.

The news reached the slaves of our creation that many Kazakh and Karakalpak tribes left their homelands and hid in the fortress of Tashkent, fearing the innumerable army of the Kalmyks.

According to the author of this source, the mountain Tajiks of Karategin and Darvaz faced the first blow, submitted to the shackles and paid the hiraj tax.

For three years starting from the spring of 1739, the Kalmyks again invaded the lands of Dashti Kipchak with a large army of 30-35 thousand people and subjugated the Big and Middle Juz of Kazakhs, the Karakalpak, Kyrgyz tribes, the East and South of Dashti Kipchak occupied their territories and then turned to Movarounnahr. Kazakh researchers J.M. As Tulibayeva noted: "... from the oppression of the Jungians, Kazakhs migrated in three directions: the Small Juz - to the west of Khiva and the Yayik and Emba valleys in the north, the Middle Juz - to the central regions of Central Asia, Samarkand and Bukhara, a "Katta Juz Kazakhs became dependent on Dzhugaria".

Galdan Syeren (1727-1745) reigned in the state of Dzhungaria, where the king was called "khuntayshi", then his uncle Syeren Dondob and generals Noyon Septen, Sari Manji, Khotal and Dagby was in command. Shubai Arslanov, a citizen of the Russian Empire, who lived in Tashkent for five months during this period, noted that a local nobleman named Husenbek was ruling in Tashkent, and Tashkent was subservient to the Kalmyks.

In Russian sources, it is noted that in 1742, after the Iranian ruler Nadirshah Afshor occupied Bukhara, Abdukarimbi went to him and asked for help in the fight against the Kalmyks, and Nadirshah sent an army of 20 thousand red-headed men to help him (based on the assumptions of historians V. Livshin and Ch. Valikhonov who gave such information, but the fact that this information was not recorded in the works of any local historians raises doubts about its truth).

Galdan Syeren, the ruler of the Kalmyks, who strengthened his rear after defeating the China-Sin Empire and making peace, entered the Ferghana Valley in 1742. Soon, the eastern part of the newly formed state was occupied by the cities of Osh, Andijan, and Margilan, and the battle continued under the walls of the Kokan fortress, which was later named the Old Horde. In such difficult moments, the population of the Kokan Khanate united, the core of the people's army and the Kokan troops consisted of settled Uzbeks, Tajiks, semi-settled Kazakhs, Karakalpak, Kipchak tribes and mountain peoples (g 'alcha) and gathered around Abdukarimbi. The governor of Ustrushana, Fazilbi Yuz, came to help with his army, and the allied forces attacked the enemy with unity and courage.

The bravery of Kokan warriors, Abdukarimbi's skillful military tactics are also recorded in written sources. The personal bravery of the Kokan troops in the defense of the Motherland became an epic in the languages of those days. In particular, a warrior named Batir Kipchak attacked the enemy ranks, attacked them and caused great losses, and he himself was killed in this battle. His bravery impressed others, and the warriors attacked the enemy fiercely after him.

The analysis of written sources emphasizes that Ustrushana warriors under the leadership of Fazilbi Yuz also made an important contribution to the decisive battles: "Only one of his soldiers

named Pirmuhammad speared ninety Kalmaks during the battle," writes Kokan historian Muhammad Hakim Khan. The unification of the forces of Abdukarimbiy and Fazilbiy made it possible to throw the Kalmyks away from the gates of Kokan, half of the forces of the defeated Kalmyks were destroyed on the battlefield, and the rest managed to escape and save their lives. Abdukarimbiy chased the enemy with the united forces and freed the Fergana Valley, Kurama (ancient Ilaq) and Tashkent regions from the enemy. This military conflict took place in 1742-1744. Relying on archive documents, researchers note that Abdukarimbiy, while sending the Kalmyk captives to their homeland in Tashkent, threw a pair of trousers on the head of one of them and told them to wait for their king Galdan-Seren in the spring of the next year (1745) for a decisive battle in the region called Quttepa, if he did not come orders him to wear the shalwar on his head and not on his legs as a sign of defeat.

Defeated by Abdukarimbi's forces, the Kalmyks did not dare to venture further into Central Asia, and in September 1745, their ruler Galdan Syeren died. His successor, Syeben Dorji Nameji, sent ambassadors to China and asked for military help as an ally against the Kokand Khanate. But the Chinese refused.

In short, it can be said that the real hero of the Kalmyks' march to the Fergana Valley was Abdukarimbiy, the ruler of the Kokan state, and the people of Ustrushana who came to their aid. The Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Kipchak, Uzbek and Tajik peoples stood shoulder to shoulder and showed examples of courage in the decisive battles to save Movarounnahr from the attack of the Kalmyks. This alliance of nations ensured a common victory over the enemy. In-depth research of the pages of the history of cooperation of fraternal nations towards a common goal is of great importance in the development of modern integration processes in Central Asia today.

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